

DESIGN OF FIBRE-POLYMER COMPOSITE STRUCTURES (CEN/TS 19101): SERVICEABILITY LIMIT STATES AND CREEP RUPTURE

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ABSTRACT

In November 2022, the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) published the Technical Specification CEN/TS 19101:2022, “Design of Fibre-Polymer Composite Structures”, which is a milestone towards the widespread application of composite materials in civil engineering structures. This paper gives an overview of the clauses about serviceability limit states (SLS) and the creep rupture verification at ultimate limit state (ULS). The SLS criteria include deflections, vibrations and matrix cracking verifications, which should consider the effects of environmental conditions and creep effects. The creep rupture of composite members and components is prevented by limiting the magnitudes of sustained stresses, using relevant quasi-permanent combinations of actions.

KEYWORDS

Fibre-polymer composites; European Technical Specification; Design code; Serviceability limit states; Creep rupture.

INTRODUCTION

In 2010, the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) decided to develop a Eurocode for fibre-polymer composite structures. For that purpose, the Working Group “Fibre Reinforced Polymer” (WG4) was established by Technical Committee 250 (TC250) of CEN. Between 2010 and 2016, members of WG4 prepared the Science and Policy Report, “*Prospect for New Guidance in the Design of FRP*” (Ascione *et al.* 2016), the first step (of three) towards the development of the future Eurocode standard. Then, between July 2018 and October 2021, CEN/TC250 appointed a Project Team (WG4.T2) under Mandate M/515 to work on the second step for the drafting of the Technical Specification (TS) CEN/TS 19101:2022, “Design of Fibre-Polymer Composite Structures”, which was published in November 2022. After a period of trial use (usually two years), the TS is expected to be converted to its Eurocode part.

CEN/TS 19101:2022 applies to buildings, bridges and other civil engineering structures, either permanent or temporary, providing a general basis for the design of all-composite structures or hybrid structures, combining composite members with members made of other materials. The TS covers three main types of composite components and members: (i) laminates (used, for instance, as plates or shells); (ii) profiles, and (iii) sandwich panels. These composite components and members can be made of different types of reinforcing fibres (scoping glass, carbon, basalt, aramid) and thermoset polymeric matrices. Polymeric foams and balsa wood can be used as core materials in sandwich panels. With respect to connections, CEN/TS 19101:2022 permits the methods of connection for structural joints to be bolted, bonded (with thermoset adhesives) and hybrid bolted-bonded.

This paper gives an overview of the clause 9 on serviceability limit states (SLS) and the sub-clause 8.5 on creep rupture at ultimate limit state (ULS), of the CEN/TS 19101:2022. The SLS criteria include deflections, vibrations and matrix cracking verifications, which should consider the effects of environmental conditions (by means of conversions factors) and creep effects (by means of creep coefficients). CEN/TS 19101:2022 provides creep coefficients for 50 years for different types and properties of fibre-polymer composites and core materials, as well as for other periods, which were determined based on a survey of test data in the public domain. Values for maximum SLS deflections and the corresponding combinations of actions are specified. For vibrations, values for the damping ratio of footbridges are suggested. When relevant, matrix cracking can be prevented by limiting the tensile strain caused by the effect of actions from the frequent combination of actions. Creep rupture (ULS) of composite members and components is prevented by limiting sustained stresses against the design values of stresses from applying the relevant quasi-permanent combinations of actions. Strength reduction factors are provided for composites with the four different types of fibres previously mentioned and for different time periods in the case of glass fibres.

CREEP EFFECTS

The mechanical properties of composites are time dependent mainly due to the viscoelastic characteristics of their polymeric matrix, which means that the composite material (as well as polymeric foams and balsa core materials) of composite structures is susceptible to the creep phenomenon. Therefore, the creep effects on the strength and deformations of composite structures shall be considered in the design. In CEN/TS 19101:2022 the creep effects on the strength of composite structures are considered as an Ultimate Limit State (ULS) through the creep rupture verification, while the creep effects on the deformations of composite structures are considered at the Serviceability Limit States (SLS), through deflection and matrix cracking verifications. Both aspects are addressed later in this paper.

The influence of the creep effect in the deformations of viscoelastic materials is generally considered by reducing the initial mean values of the relevant elastic moduli of materials ($X_m(0)$), at time equal to zero, through a creep coefficient at time t (taken in years), $\phi(t)$, when verifications involving such moduli are necessary. Thus, the mean value of elastic modulus or shear modulus at time t , considering the creep effects, $X_m(t)$, can be expressed as:

$$X_m(t) = X_m(0) \cdot \phi(t) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

It should be noted that Equation 1 considers an apparent reduction in the elastic moduli of materials to determine long-term effects. However, the actual values of elastic moduli used to determine the momentary response of composite structures or their dynamic behaviour remain unaffected.

CEN/TS 19101:2022 provides values of creep coefficients for different elastic moduli of pultruded composite profiles, composite laminates/plies and core materials, respectively, reproduced in Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3. The proposed values in these three tables for the creep coefficients are valid for linear viscoelasticity. This depends on the stress levels and also on the environmental conditions (temperature and relative humidity), which need to remain relatively low. In this context, limit values of temperature and relative humidity are given in the captions of the tables that were taken from the informative Appendix A of CEN/TS 19101:2022.

The values for the creep coefficients given in these tables for different elastic moduli of respectively, pultruded FRP profiles, FRP laminates/plies and core materials, were defined based on: (i) data available in the technical literature; and (ii) considering recommendations already provided in other design guidelines or standards. The rationale for the creep coefficients in the tables is detailed in the Commentary to CEN/TS 19101:2022.

Table 1: Values for the $\phi(t)$ for different elastic moduli of pultruded composite profiles (glass, carbon or basalt fibres; fibre volume fraction of at least 35%; temperature up to 25 °C; relative humidity up to 65%) – extracted from CEN/TS 19101:2022

Property	Period of time (years)										
	1	5	10	15	20	25	30	40	50	75	100
E_x^{full}	0.25	0.38	0.46	0.51	0.55	0.58	0.61	0.66	0.70	0.78	0.84
G_{xy}^{full}	0.57	0.98	1.23	1.40	1.54	1.66	1.76	1.94	2.09	2.39	2.62
$E_{x,t}$	0.20	0.22	0.24	0.24	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.26	0.26	0.27	0.28
$E_{x,c}$	0.20	0.23	0.27	0.30	0.32	0.34	0.36	0.38	0.41	0.45	0.48

Notes:

- E_x^{full} is the effective full-section flexural modulus of the pultruded composite profile
- G_{xy}^{full} is the effective full-section shear modulus of the pultruded composite profile
- $E_{x,t}$ is the in-plane tensile modulus in x direction of the pultruded composite profile
- $E_{x,c}$ is the in-plane compressive modulus in x direction of the pultruded composite profile

Table 2: Values for the $\phi(t)$ for different elastic moduli of composite laminates/plies (glass, carbon or basalt fibres; fibre volume fraction of at least 35%; temperature up to 25 °C; relative humidity up to 65%) – extracted from CEN/TS 19101:2022

Type of fibres	Property	Period of time (years)										
		1	5	10	15	20	25	30	40	50	75	100
UD	$E_{x,t}$	0.10	0.11	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.15
	$E_{x,c}$	0.15	0.23	0.27	0.30	0.32	0.34	0.36	0.38	0.41	0.45	0.48
	G_{xy}	1.13	1.55	1.78	1.94	2.06	2.16	2.25	2.40	2.52	2.78	2.94
Woven (0/90°)	$E_{x,t}, E_{x,c}$	0.44	0.53	0.58	0.60	0.62	0.64	0.65	0.67	0.68	0.71	0.73
CSM	$E_{x,t}, E_{x,c}$	1.48	1.91	2.12	2.25	2.34	2.42	2.48	2.58	2.67	2.82	2.93

Notes:

- $E_{x,t}$ is the in-plane tensile modulus in x direction of the composite laminates/plies
- $E_{x,c}$ is the in-plane compressive modulus in x direction of the composite laminates/plies
- G_{xy} is the in-plane shear modulus of composite laminates/plies

Table 3: Values the $\phi(t)$ for different out-of-plane shear modulus, G_{xz} , of different core materials (temperature up to 22 °C for polymeric foams and up to 25 °C for balsa wood; relative humidity up to 65%) – extracted from CEN/TS 19101:2022

Material	Property	Period of time (years)										
		1	5	10	15	20	25	30	40	50	75	100
PUR foam (up to 100 kg/m ³)	G_{xz}	3.34	4.19	4.60	4.86	5.05	5.20	5.33	5.54	5.70	6.01	6.24
PET foam (up to 100 kg/m ³)	G_{xz}	0.03	0.21	0.31	0.38	0.44	0.49	0.53	0.60	0.65	0.77	0.86
End-grain balsa (up to 100 kg/m ³)	G_{xz}	0.70	1.59	2.11	2.47	2.74	2.97	3.16	3.49	3.75	4.28	4.69

SERVICEABILITY LIMIT STATES (SLS)

Composite structures, like other structures of other types of structural materials, shall be designed and constructed such that all relevant serviceability criteria are satisfied, namely those given in EN 1990. CEN/TS 19101:2022 explicitly includes the following SLS verifications:

- Deflections, which adversely affect the appearance of the structure, the comfort of users and the functionality of the structure, or cause damage to the finishing and/or other non-structural elements;
- Vibrations, that cause discomfort to users or limit the functional effectiveness of the structure;
- Matrix cracking, which affects the appearance, the durability or functionality of the structure.

Deflections

The control of deflections can be done by limiting their values to maximum permitted values. These maximum permitted values may be specified by the relevant authorities or, where not specified, agreed for a specific project by relevant parties. Tables A.1.10 and A.1.11 in EN 1990 include suggested values of maximum permitted vertical and horizontal deflections for buildings, unless the National Annex of a country provides different ones. For the sake of clarity, Table 4 includes suggested maximum vertical deflections for non-industrial buildings included in EN 1990. The example chosen is the particular case for internal partition walls not reinforced of floors and accessible roofs.

The determination of the maximum deflections of a composite member or structure should be done: (i) by adopting the relevant actions and combinations of actions, as per EN 1990; (ii) by using mean values of elastic moduli; (iii) by accounting for the environmental conditions through the appropriate conversion factors of temperature (η_{ct}) and moisture (η_{cm}); and (iv) by considering the creep effects.

Characteristic, frequent and quasi-permanent combinations of actions may be used in design to control the value of design deflections. Characteristic combinations of actions are normally used to verify if the excessive deformations in the members or structures can lead to irreversible effects or permanent damage, namely in non-structural members. Frequent combinations of actions and the frequent value of variable actions are normally used to assess deflection effects that are reversible. Quasi-permanent combinations of actions are normally used to assess long-term (creep) deformation effects and to control the appearance of members or structures.

The control of vertical deflections in accordance with EN 1990 requires the following deflections to be calculated (see Figure 1, in which L is the span of a beam member):

- w_c is the precamber in the unloaded structural member (if applied);
- w_1 is the initial part of the deflection under permanent loads of the relevant combination of actions;
- w_2 is the long-term part of the deflection under permanent loads including quasi-permanent loads;
- w_3 is the instantaneous deflection due to variable actions excluding the quasi-permanent loads;
- w_{tot} is the total deflection as the sum of w_1 , w_2 , w_3 ;
- w_{max} is the remaining total deflection taking into account the precamber.

Figure 1: Components of vertical deflection

Table 4: Suggested maximum vertical deflections for non-industrial buildings (extracted from Table A.1.10 (NDP) of EN 1990)

Serviceability criteria	Limiting damage to elements other than structural	Comfort of users	Appearance
Combinations of actions to be considered	Characteristic	Frequent combination	Quasi-permanent
Floor, accessible roof: Internal partition walls not reinforced - partitions of brittle material or non-flexible	$w_2 + w_3 \leq L/500$	$w_2 + w_3 \leq L/300$	$w_1 + w_2 - w_c \leq L/250$
Floor, accessible roof: Internal partition walls not reinforced - partitions of non-brittle materials	$w_2 + w_3 \leq L/400$	$w_2 + w_3 \leq L/300$	$w_1 + w_2 - w_c \leq L/250$

The mechanical properties of composite materials, core materials and adhesives are affected by environmental conditions, particularly temperature and moisture. Accordingly, conversion factors for temperature and moisture are provided in CEN/TS 19101:2022. For the assessment of deflections, these conversion factors need to be considered for the stiffness-related properties of these materials.

As mentioned above, the influence of the creep phenomenon in generating deformations is generally quantified by means of a creep coefficient at time t of loading, $\phi(t)$, defined as the ratio between the creep deformation (or creep deflection), $w_{\text{creep}}(t)$, and the initial deformation (or instantaneous deflection), w_{inst} . Thus, the creep deflection can be expressed as:

$$w_{\text{creep}}(t) = w_{\text{inst}} \cdot \phi(t) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Note that in Equation (2), it is considered, as a simplifying assumption, that deflection only depends on a single elastic modulus. In composite members, namely those in bending, this is usually not the case, since shear deformations are usually relevant. Moreover, in sandwich structures, the creep deformations in both face sheets and core materials also need to be considered. Therefore, in general, the creep coefficients associated to each relevant material and elastic moduli need to be considered when determining creep deflections.

In general, for SLS design, composite structures present linear elastic behaviour. Thus, a linear relationship between the effect of actions from loads and the corresponding member or structure deformations can be assumed. This assumption, provided that the external constraints are bilateral, allows for the determination of the final deflection as the summation of the individual deflection contributions due to permanent and variable loads. On the other hand, if the time-dependent deformations of these composite components can be described by a ‘global’ creep coefficient, $\phi(t)$, then the long-term deflection can be obtained by the sum of the different contributions at time t , under the assumption of linear creep behaviour.

Taking w_{G_k} as the instantaneous deflection due to permanent loads ($\sum_i G_{k,i}$), the corresponding long-term deflection due to these loads at time t is given by,

$$w_{G_k}(t) = w_{G_k} \cdot \phi(t) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

It is commonly assumed that for variable actions only the quasi-permanent component of loading produces creep deformation (which is a long-term effect), see e.g. EN 1995-1-1. Therefore, regardless

of the type of combination of actions, the long-term deflection of the variable action j at time t , is given by,

$$w_{Q_{k,j}}(t) = \psi_{2,j} \cdot w_{Q_{k,j}} \cdot \phi(t) \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where $w_{Q_{k,j}}$ is the instantaneous deflection of a variable action j ($Q_{k,j}$) and $\psi_{2,j}$ is the combination factor applied to variable action j to determine its quasi-permanent value.

Based on the previous discussion, CEN/TS 19101:2022 provide the equations for the determination of deflections w_1 , w_2 and w_3 for the relevant combinations of actions. A summary of the equations for the three deflections is presented in Table 5 as a function of the type of combination of actions.

Table 5: Equations of w_1 , w_2 and w_3 as function of the combination of actions (assumption that deflection only depends on a single elastic modulus)

Combination of actions	Characteristic	Frequent combination	Quasi-permanent
w_1	--	--	w_{G_k}
w_2	$\left(w_{G_k} + \sum_j \psi_{2,j} \cdot w_{Q_{k,j}} \right) \cdot \phi(t)$		
w_3	$w_{Q_{k,1}} + \sum_{j>1} \psi_{0,j} \cdot w_{Q_{k,j}}$	$\psi_{1,1} \cdot w_{Q_{k,1}}$	--

Vibrations

Whenever relevant, measures should be taken to prevent structural vibrations that cause discomfort to people or limit the functional effectiveness of a structure or part thereof. Therefore, the natural frequency of vibrations of the structure or structural member should be kept above appropriate values. A.1.7.3 of EN 1990 provides instructions for vibration verifications.

In accordance with EN 1990, the minimum values of natural frequencies for a structure or a structural member should be as agreed on a project-by-project basis by relevant parties, depending upon the function of the structure, the structural materials and the dynamic source of the vibration. Therefore, if a natural vibration frequency of the structure is lower than the appropriate value, analysis of the dynamic response of the structure should be carried out. Proper values for damping need to be used in structural analyses to obtain realistic dynamic responses. CEN/TS 19101:2022 recommends conservative values for the damping ratio of 0.4% and 1.0%, respectively, for the structural analysis of footbridges of consequence classes CC3 and CC4 (EN 1990), and for other footbridges. Existing data on damping ratios of fibre-polymer composite structures is scarce and the proposed values were based on the research study by Wei *et al.* (2019). Further details are included in the Commentary to CEN/TS 19101:2022.

Matrix cracking

Matrix cracking can be relevant for the in-service performance of composite structures under exposure class II (e.g. outdoors exposure conditions without continuous exposure to water), and under exposure to class III (e.g. continuous exposure to water or seawater). Therefore, to prevent matrix cracking, CEN/TS 19101:2022 limits the tensile strain under the frequent combination of actions, $\varepsilon_{t,SLS}$, including effects of creep from permanent and quasi-permanent loads to the design value of the tensile strain causing matrix cracking, $\varepsilon_{t,d}^{crack}$, i.e.

$$\varepsilon_{t,SLS} \leq \varepsilon_{t,d}^{crack} = \frac{\varepsilon_{t,k}^{crack}}{\gamma_m} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

Where γ_m is the partial factor of the composite material (tensile strength), which depends on the coefficient of variation of such property, and $\varepsilon_{t,k}^{\text{crack}}$ is the characteristic value of the tensile strain causing matrix cracking. Values of 0.3% and 0.6% are suggested for $\varepsilon_{t,k}^{\text{crack}}$, in the case of composite laminates with matrices of polyester or epoxy resins, respectively. The rationale for the adopted verification and proposed values are detailed in the Commentary to CEN/TS 19101:2022.

CREEP RUPTURE (ULS)

Fibre-polymer composite materials under sustained stresses, namely tensile, compressive, bending and/or shear stresses, can fail suddenly after a period of time, due to a phenomenon known as creep rupture (tertiary creep). Therefore, creep rupture of composite members and components must be prevented by limiting the values of sustained stresses. Under the quasi-permanent combination of actions for the design against fibre-dominated creep rupture failure, CEN/TS 19101:2022 imposes the following condition to the design value of the maximum sustained tensile ($\sigma_{t,\text{creep,Ed}}$) or compressive ($\sigma_{c,\text{creep,Ed}}$) stress, that is generated from the effect of actions:

$$\sigma_{t,\text{creep,Ed}} \leq \sigma_{t,\text{creep,Rd}} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$\sigma_{c,\text{creep,Ed}} \leq \sigma_{c,\text{creep,Rd}} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where the design values of the tensile or compressive stress limit, are given by,

$$\sigma_{t,\text{creep,Rd}} = \frac{\eta_c}{\gamma_{M,\text{creep}}} \cdot k_{t,\text{creep}} \cdot f_{i,t,k} \quad \text{in the case of tensile stress} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

$$\sigma_{c,\text{creep,Rd}} = \frac{\eta_c}{\gamma_{M,\text{creep}}} \cdot k_{c,\text{creep}} \cdot f_{i,c,k} \quad \text{in the case of compressive stress} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where η_c is the conversion factor due to temperature and moisture effects ($\eta_c = \eta_{ct} \cdot \eta_{cm}$), $\gamma_{M,\text{creep}}$ is the partial factor for creep rupture (the recommended value is 1.5, based on engineering judgement given the present lack of data for performing reliability analyses for partial factor calibration), $k_{t,\text{creep}}$ and $k_{c,\text{creep}}$ are the strength reduction factors for creep rupture in tension and compression for continuous unidirectional fibres (see Table 6), and $f_{i,t,k}$ and $f_{i,c,k}$ are characteristic values of the tensile and compressive strengths, respectively, of the composite laminate in the fibre i direction.

Table 6: Strength reduction factors $k_{t,\text{creep}}$ (tensile) and $k_{c,\text{creep}}$ (compressive) for creep rupture of continuous unidirectional fibres, different types of fibres and a period of 50 years (extracted from CEN/TS 19101:2022)

Type of stress	Glass	Aramid (*)	Basalt (*)	Carbon (*)
Tensile	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.9
Compressive	0.75×0.4	0.75×0.5	0.75×0.6	0.75×0.9

(*) Values also valid for 100 years.

The values for $k_{t,\text{creep}}$ were derived from an extensive literature review, which is mainly summarized in ACI 440.1R-1 and Benmorkane *et al.* (2019), for the case of glass, aramid and carbon fibres, and mainly by test results in composite bars used to reinforce concrete. Only three relevant studies were found addressing the creep rupture stress limit for basalt composites, from which a value of 0.6 was proposed for $k_{t,\text{creep}}$, supported by engineering judgement. Further details can be found in the Commentary to CEN/TS 19101:2022.

Table 6 presents the estimated reduction factors of composites with aramid, basalt and carbon that are valid for time periods of 50 and 100 years. In fact, according to published data the reductions in

$k_{t,creep}$ is 5%, 3% and 0% between 50 and 100 years for aramid, basalt and carbon fibre-types (see Commentary to CEN/TS 19101:2022).

In CEN/TS 19101:2022 it is assumed that the ULS resistance to creep rupture failure under compressive stresses in the fibre direction of the member is lower than the corresponding resistance under tensile stresses, since in compression the viscoelastic effects of the matrix can reduce fibre support against fibre buckling. Using engineering judgement, $k_{c,creep}$ was set as 0.75 of $k_{t,creep}$ for each of the four fibre-types presented in Table 6. The confirmation of this assumption requires experimental testing.

In the case of composite laminates with glass fibres, CEN/TS 19101:2022 also provides extrapolation formulas of the tensile and compressive strength reduction factors, for periods different than 50 years, as function of the time, t , in hours, respectively,

$$k_{t,creep}(t) = 0.9 - 0.088 \cdot \lg(t) \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

$$k_{c,creep}(t) = 0.75 \cdot k_{t,creep}(t) \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

Equation 8 was formulated based on the following assumptions that are detailed in the Commentary to CEN/TS 19101:2022: (i) linear evolution of $k_{t,creep}(t)$ with time in logarithmic scale; (ii) $k_{t,creep}$ equal to 0.4 at 50 years (as in Table 6); and, (iii) $k_{t,creep}$ equal to 0.9 at 1 hour, which is $\lg(0)$. The latter value was set by the project team using engineering judgement. These assumptions ensured that between 50 and 100 years the predicted value of $k_{t,creep}$ will be lower than the value given by Benmokrane *et al.* (2019) for the lower bound 99% prediction interval (main work used to support this provision), as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Extrapolated logarithmic time-to-failure (creep-rupture) curves for the sustained tensile stress applied as a percent of the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of bars of continuous glass fibre polymer composites

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper presented how the European Technical Specification CEN/TS 19101:2022 addresses creep deformation effects by using prescribed creep coefficients. The methodologies and rationale adopted are common to the other Eurocodes and the proposed values are supported by data in existing literature and guidelines.

Subsequently, the clause for the design of serviceability limit states (SLS) is addressed, by including the verification criteria for deflections, vibrations and matrix cracking. Most of the provisions follow the

Eurocode guidance given in the EN 1990. Again, the proposed values are supported by data in existing literature and guidelines.

Finally, the design procedure for failure by creep rupture (an ultimate limit state (ULS) verification) is presented. To carry out the design verifications, strength reduction factors for creep rupture are presented for composites with four different types of reinforcing fibres and for different time periods. These factors are supported by data in existing literature and guidelines (when available) and by engineering judgement when there is a lack of data.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.